

ISic3613

I.Sicily inscription 3613

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Camarina

Place of origin (modern)

Kamarina

Provenance

contrada Maestro, Camarina

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Kamarina, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Kamarina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645686

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 58.1042

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 2009.0567

Metcalfe, M. 2008. Una iscrizione arcaica dal Maestro. In Militello, P.(eds.), *Scicli:*

archeologia e territorio. Palermo. pp. 227-230.

Di Stefano, G. 2013. Camarina. Le acquisizioni, il museo tematico, la collezione "Biagio Pace", il lapidario. Ispica. At 29

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